

ENERGY ABSORPTION IN BALLISTIC PERFORATION OF GRAPHITE EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The work deals with the energy absorption of graphite/epoxy laminated plates due to spherical projectile impact. A scanning electron microscopic examination of a few fragments from the impact shows that the fracture surfaces of the matrix have some characteristic hacklemarks. An attempt is being made to determine if these hacklemarks are responsible for the considerable energy absorption of the impact.

Key words: impact, ballistic tests, micrograph, composites, high velocity impact, projectile, graphite/epoxy, fracture, dynamic fracture.

INTRODUCTION

New composites manufactured from advanced fibers and specially selected resins are being increasingly considered for defeating high speed projectiles or ballistic threats. The ability of graphite/epoxy (Gr/Ep) composites for this purpose is being considered. The ability of such material clearly relates to its energy absorbing properties at very high strain rates (10^3 to 10^5s^{-1}), and the amount of material which is involved in the energy absorbing process (Brown and Egglestone, 1989).

Initial work on energy absorption by 32-ply Gr/Ep composite plate subjected to a wide range of impact velocity was conducted in the ballistic test range of the Flight Dynamics Laboratory at the U.S. Air Force Wright-Patterson Air Force base, Ohio. Results of these tests have not yet been published but summarized by Altamirano (1991) and Mayer (1992) and is shown in Figure 1. The empirical relationship between the energy absorption function E , and the impact velocity V has been characterized by them as:

$$E = CV^n \quad (1)$$

Ballistic tests were also conducted at the U.S. Army Cold Regions Research and Engineering Laboratory, Hanover, New Hampshire on single and multiple ply laminates to study the impact damage and energy absorption characteristics. Common to both U.S. Air Force, Wright Laboratory test and the U.S. Army Cold Regions Laboratory (CRREL) test are some micrographs of fragments from the impact which contained very characteristic comblike hacklemarks.

The periodicity of hacklemarks due to impact and fracture is at present intriguing. As of now, there is no explanation reported in

the literature for a satisfactory explanation of such periodicity. It is possible that such periodicity is a result of standing waves in the matrix, that is the resonance of the cavity between fibers. The wavelength of hacklemarks corresponds to the various modes of vibration and the periodicity to the shear yielding failure of the material. A basis for consideration of these hacklemarks as an energy absorption mechanism is discussed in the latter part of this paper.

ENERGY DISSIPATION IN PERFORATION IMPACT

The study of energy dissipation of laminated plates under perforation impact provides an estimate of the available energy which causes the various forms of damage to the composite plate.

Energy absorbed by the Gr/Ep plate can be computed from the following energy balance equation (Greszczuk 1982, Shivakumar et al. 1985):

$$E_A = E_c + E_b + E_m + E_d + E_f \quad (2)$$

where E_c = the energy expended in Hertzian contact indentation, E_b = the energy due to plate bending, E_m = the energy due to stretching of the middle plate surface, E_d = the energy due to permanent plate damage, and E_f = the energy due to friction, heating etc. Among all these energies, in the perforation type impact the permanent plate damage is the main source of energy absorption. Plate damage may include any or all of the following modes of failure: Matrix cracking, delamination, fiber breakage, spalling, and shear plug out.

The high strain rate Hertzian contact deformation work has been conducted at CRREL using Hopkinson bar apparatus and is reported in detail in another paper in this conference (Dutta et al 1993) and earlier by Dutta et al (1991). As the projectile impacts the plate a given amount of energy is dissipated in causing the plate to flex before any irreversible damage process begins. Following the flexure the permanent damage and failure of the plate is initiated. As mentioned before, this phase is characterized by fiber breakage, fiber pullout, matrix crack, and delaminations. If the areas of delamination could be determined an estimate of the energy absorbed by the delamination process can be obtained. The next major source of energy absorption is in shear plug out. The plug out is a shear fracture conoid having smaller diameter on the impact side and larger diameter on the exit side. Florence (1969) estimated that the circular area over which the impact momentum is first distributed is the base diameter of the fracture conoid and is equal to the diameter of the projectile. The empirical observation of the cone angle is approximately 63° .

BALLISTIC TESTS

The ballistic experimental test facilities at CRREL is shown schematically in Figure 2(a) and by an assembly photograph in Figure 2(b). The entire facility is located in three adjoining rooms. The gun room is equipped with a 14.3 mm (9/16 in.) bore explosive powered gun which can be remotely operated from the control room. The barrel end and the projectile path is completely sealed with a steel pipe which passes through the wall of the gun room into the target room. The end of the seal pipe terminates into a specially designed

plexiglass chamber, equipped to clamp the target test plates at the periphery for normal impact. The target test chamber is also completely sealed with the target located in the middle. The back plate of the chamber, made from plastic is replacable after every shot. The projectile exiting through the back plate is captured by a sandbox located in the flight path opposite to an opening in the wall. For high velocity (>610 m/s, 2000 ft/s) tests the interior of the gun barrel, seal pipe and the test chamber must have a very high vacuum pressure which is achieved by connecting the pipe interior to a vacuum pump. For low velocity tests no vacuum is necessary.

The impact and exit velocities were measured using light activated chronograph screens used in pairs on both sides of the target. The output from the chronograph screen starts and stops a timer with 10^{-7} second accuracy.

To perform the tests the 12.7 mm (0.5 in) diameter steel sphere projectile is first located in the gun with a suitable sabot. The amount of gun powder necessary to propel the projectile at the desired velocity was first determined by trial runs. When the projectile crosses the light path of the first chronograph screen it starts the counting clock. When it passes the next one the signal from it stops the counting, thus displaying the time of travel on the time counter. By measuring the distance between the two light screens the projectile velocity is calculated.

The tests were performed on two types of Gr/Ep plates. The first system is identified as T300/984 unidirectional 8-ply laminate. The second system was a 30-ply AS-4/3502 laminate with a stacking sequence of

$$[(-45/0_2)_2/90/-45/0_2/-45]_8$$

No attempt was made to capture the fragments from the impact on the unidirectional composite. The focus of the unidirectional composite impact test was to identify the gross damage pattern developed on the composite at different velocities. The fragments from the quasi-isotropic composites were collected on the adhesive coated papers which lined the interior of the target chamber on both the impact and exit sides. Figure 3 shows one typical perforated plate of unidirectional Gr/Ep, and Figure 4 shows a carefully cut section through the 30-ply quasi-isotropic Gr/Ep. The results of only room temperature unidirectional plate impacts will now be discussed.

DAMAGE ANALYSIS

The damages in the unidirectional laminate were simple to interpret. Because of severe anisotropy of the stiffness and strength properties, only longitudinal cracks in fiber direction propagated. The primary failure in the impact zone was obviously indentation followed by fiber breakage, delamination, and finally shear plugging. Numerous longitudinal cracks split the specimens in a large number of longitudinal strips (Figure 3). Figure 5 shows the effects of velocity on the damage process of the unidirectional Gr/Ep. Notice that the shear plug out hole for the high velocity (4500 ft/s) impact has a much cleaner outline (Figure 5a) than the one at lower velocity (Figure 5b). It seems likely that at higher velocities more momentum is trapped in the shear plug than at low velocities. At lower velocities the fibers break upon impact of the projectile, and then

flex with shear failures propagating longitudinally to the boundaries of the specimens.

Figure 6(a) shows a very low velocity (88.4 m/s, 291 ft/s) impact of the steel ball on the 30-ply Gr/Ep laminate. The energy of impact in this case was not sufficient to cause perforation. (Ballistic tests performed at the U.S. Airforce Wright Research Laboratory (Mayer 1992) show that the V_{50} velocities for this type of laminates would be about 137 m/s (450 ft/s). Nevertheless, the damage by delamination and fiber breakage did happen as evident from the slight bulging of the rear surface.

At velocities around V_{50} a typical damage looks like the one shown in Figure 6(b), which was obtained at 151 m/s (496 ft/s). The perforation was complete in this case.

The high velocity (975 m/s, 3200 ft/s) perforation type damage on these laminate was rather extensive. Figure 6(c) shows a cutout section through the perforation hole of the high velocity impact. The cutout was carefully made without disturbing the positions of broken lamina and fibers. Notice that the damages on both impact and exit sides are more extensive than than at the center. Delamination damage is more in the rear side, whereas the impact end has more crushing and fiber breakage.

SEM ANALYSIS OF BALLISTIC FRAGMENTS

As mentioned before, the composite fragments from the 30-ply Gr/Ep target panels were collected on the adhesive coated paper, lining the target test chamber. The SEM of one of the particles shows very well developed hackle mark (Figure 7a). In the second particle (Figure 7b) the hackle mark is less developed but appears to be of higher frequencies. Similar hackle marks were also noted by Mayer (1992) in the SEM analysis of fragments from ballistics tests on Gr/Ep at AFWL.

DISCUSSION

The results of non-perforated low velocity impact, perforated low velocity impact, and the perforated high velocity impact manifest the progressive failure mechanisms, one taking over the other, as the velocity increases. For example, in the nonperforated low velocity impact on the multiple ply laminate the Hertzian indentation was the major form of damage, whereas at higher velocities shear plug out with extensive compressive failure and delaminations were the main mechanisms.

The fractographic features and its relation to the failure are of interest to note. Very little information on the genesis of hackle mark formation is available in composites literature except that a large number of researchers have observed their presence related with brittle failure (Morris 1982, Richards-Frandsen and Naerheim 1983). It has been shown by Purslow (1986) that in static failure, the presence of the relatively stiff fibers increases the influence of shear stresses on the resin fracture and hackle marks development under such conditions will be suppressed. However, Purslow observed that at relatively high strain rate of deformation and fracture matrix

cleavage and hackle formation are common. SEM's of ballistic fragments of the Gr/Ep from two independent laboratories (WPAFB and CRREL) clearly show that above V_{50} there are indications of hacklemark development.

The hacklemarks present a periodic formation of sigmoidally shaped ridges and troughs running roughly parallel to the fiber direction and located in the matrix region between them. The spatial periodicity is manifested in a direction parallel to the fibers. This regular spatial periodicity is the first suggestive observation. The second observation is that the wavelength of these hacklemarks appears to increase as the distance between the neighbouring fibers increase (Figure 7a). The wavelength of the hacklemark is of the order of inter-fiber distance. Sometimes, the ridges appear to be canted at an angle to the fiber axis.

It is appropriate now to examine the phenomenon of wavelength proportionality to fiber spacing at some depth. It is conceivable that the wavelength proportionality to fiber spacing would result if it were associated with or determined by a disturbance which propagates in the plane of two adjacent fibers from one fiber surface to the other at a fixed angle to their length direction and then was reflected back from the other fiber at an equal angle toward the first fiber, and the process then repeated. The distance between successive reflections from the same fiber then represents a wavelength. Its proportionality to interfiber separation follows from the geometric similarity of the construction of wave reflections. Such constructions are current in models of the acoustic resonance frequencies of simple enclosures (Beranek and Leo, 1954).

The explanation offered here is that the hacklemarks result from intense resonant vibrations of the matrix polymer cavity contained between the points of closest proximity of two adjacent fibers. These oscillations are considered to be so intense that the brittle matrix polymer is pulverized in regions surrounding the antinodes of these standing wave vibrational modes. The shape of these hacklemarks are therefore reflections of both the failure stress criterion and the intensity of vibration present in the composite during the impact event.

We consider that the hacklemarks represent a significant augmentation of the surface area of a fragment and therefore also a correspondingly large store of surface free energy. We speculate that the spatial frequency must increase with the speed of impact since our observations had been that the total energy absorbed (as measured by the decrease in kinetic energy of the projectile) increased with the velocity of the impact and a higher spatial frequency would represent an increase in surface area assuming the amplitude of the undulations remained constant. It is also conjectured that if the spatial frequency of the hacklemarks did not increase with projectile speed, then perhaps the fractional coverage of the surface of a fragment by hacklemarks must reflect the increase in total impact energy absorbed. Of course, we are aware from the work of Dennis Grady (1982) at Sandia Laboratories, of the decrease in the mean size of fragments produced as the strain rate is increased which results in a greater density of the energy absorption per unit volume of the fractured and fragmented material. We have appropriated these results to the case of impact by postulating a proportionality between strain rate and projectile velocity. We now hypothesize that the hacklemark wave length is a function only of the inter-fiber space occupied by

matrix, and the distance between transverse matrix and their characteristic length is associated with the rate of impact event. We should continue to expect that the percentage coverage of the interply surface region by hacklemarks should increase with the vehemence of the impact (that is, the strain rate or projectile arrival velocity) and that the amount of material missing from the region occupied by hacklemarks should likewise increase with the applied intensity of the impact.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Initial results from ballistic impact tests have shown increased energy absorption at higher impact velocities. An analysis of the energy partitioning between various mechanisms of energy absorption is important in understanding the ballistic impact resistance of the material. Laminated plates have a unique failure mechanism in the ability to delaminate, which is the most favorable mode of failure for preventing penetration. This study has attempted to relate this energy to the micrographic features of the fractures on the delaminated surfaces to the energy level (velocity level). Fracture surfaces from fragments of ballistic impact have shown a tendency to develop characteristic hacklemarks. Their developments have been related to the cavity resonance of the matrix between the fibers. Although qualitative indications point to the existence of these phenomena a quantitative analysis is still lacking.

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Figure 1. Ballistic test results of 31-ply Gr/Ep plate 12.7-mm steel sphere impact. (Mayer, 1992).

Figure 2. (a) Schematic of CRREL ballistic test facility.
 (b) Assembly of the CRREL ballistic test gun system.

Figure 3. A typical specimen of the unidirectional Gr/Ep specimen after test.

Figure 4. Section of a 30-ply Gr/Ep panel through the perforation.

(a) High velocity: shear plug out.

(b) Low velocity: no shear plug out.

Figure 5. Effect of velocity on the damage of unidirectional Gr/Ep plates:

PANEL 1

(a) Very low velocity indentation impact.

PANEL 2

(b) Low velocity impact damage.

(c) High velocity impact damage

Figure 6.

Figure 7a
Well-Developed Hackle-marked
Fracture Surface

Figure 7b
Less-Developed Hackle-marked
Fracture Surface